

THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN LANGUAGE AND SOCIETY.

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Annotation:

This article discusses the science of sociolinguistics, its object of study, language and social relations, language and society relations, the impact of changes in society on language, which emerged at the intersection of linguistics with sociology.

Keywords: linguistics, sociology, anthropocentrism, social factors, language policy, speech, linguistic factor.

As language is a social phenomenon, it is inextricably linked with society and its life. The study of issues such as the social nature of language, its social function, the impact of changes in society on language, the role of language policy in the development of language, intersected the science of linguistics with the science of sociology. The study of sociolinguistics, which results from the intersection of two independent disciplines at one point, is conducted under the name of sociology of language and studies the relationship between society and language. The term sociolinguistics is made up of two components, the Latin words "social" and "lingua". Sociolinguistics is used in linguistics in the following senses:

1. The relationship between language and society, that is, the role of language in the life and development of society, and vice versa, the role of society in the development of language.

2. Differences in language due to the social grouping of the nation. Language is a manifestation of the human mind. Moreover, the human mind is the highest product of nature's many millions of years of evolution. In this sense, language as an expression of our mind and our language through our mind cannot be compared to anything else, an event, and a process. Naturally, like any social event and phenomenon, language develops in the process of different views, thoughts, and struggles. The struggle for language, in turn, is not just a matter of rules for the inner life of language, of their accuracy and validity. The struggle for language is, first, a struggle for the place of language in society. Today the processes of globalization and the growth of scientific and technological achievements are accelerating to such an extent that many national languages

are unable to withstand their pressure, intensity and pressure, and are declining under the influence of other languages. In the current state of development, it is important to keep in mind that today is a time of intensification of dialogue and relations between nations, countries and states. No nation in society can live on its own, in isolation from other nations. They have to be in constant economic and spiritual contact and communication. Such attitudes and dialogue will accelerate the development of nations; pave the way for rapid acquaintance with innovations and discoveries in science, technology and industry, spirituality and culture. This, in turn, requires learning the languages of other peoples. After all, learning a foreign language is a social event. Learning a foreign language gives you the opportunity to learn a different culture. I, in turn, adopt the concepts and views of culture in our social environment and evaluate this culture in terms of the concepts of our national culture. As mentioned above, language has a social character since its inception. Because language originated in a group of people, in the process of social work, it serves to communicate, to exchange ideas. Language is a social weapon that exists only in society, among people. The fate of language is linked to the fate of society. The object of sociolinguistics is to study the effect of language on changes in society. Sociological research is usually conducted in two or more areas. I will consider some of these parameters. The object of sociological research includes various social elements, namely the features related to language differences.

The amount of these elements may change over time, but basic research emphasizes the following three elements:

- 1) the transmitter of information;
- 2) the recipient;
- 3) environment.

I. The social background of the communicator is more pronounced in some industry-specific dialects. This is the case, for example, in many Hindu dialects. I also see this in the conversations between men and women. It depends on the perception of the community by the person transmitting the information.

II. The social background of the person receiving the speech is more specific to Eastern languages. For example, when addressing an adult, it is used as a sign of respect. Another unique style of speech is children's speech, which is not only the way children speak, but also the way adults speak to children in many languages.

III. The third element is the environment, which includes all the elements of speech other than the above. Examples of this are the terms that have emerged in almost all languages due to the social environment.

In the current period of development, because of the rapid development of science, in our daily lives, almost every day there is a discovery. As a result, the language lexicon is enriched with new terms. An invention created in another country is usually named after a language that is used in that country. As the invention spread to other countries, a new word entered the lexicon of the language of that country and soon began to be actively used. In this case, too, I can see an example of the influence of society on language. At first glance the introduction of such words may seem insignificant, but it is also true that over time, the number of such words increases in number and seriously impairs the purity of the language. The issue of language and society relations is also a topical issue in the territory of one country. In linguistics, this term, called bilingualism, refers to the use of another language in parallel with one's mother tongue. For example, the Kazakh and Kyrgyz peoples use Russian in their daily lives in parallel with their mother tongue. In the case of bilingualism, of course, the two languages interact. In this case, it is natural that there is a lot of confusion in people's speech. This condition is especially common in young children. This is because when a child grows up in a bilingual family, he or she will be able to communicate in those two languages, but his or her vocabulary may be lower than that of people who speak fewer languages. The study of such issues is also the task of sociolinguistics.

Conclusion: I can say that just as a society is in constant motion, in development, in change, so its language is in constant motion, in change, in development. Among the researches on language in modern linguistics, identification and analysis of social factors influencing language is one of the priorities of modern sociolinguistics. Today, when social development is developing rapidly, one of our main tasks is to

preserve the purity of our native language, to ensure its low status among the world's languages.

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